

THE ROLE OF THE LAW IN SOCIETY

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Abstract. Law is a set of rules that are created and are enforceable by social or governmental institutions to regulate behavior, with its precise definition a matter of longstanding debate. It has been variously described as a science and as the art of justice. This article describes about the role of the law in today's society.

Keywords: constitution, society, the rule of the law, prevail of the law.

A society is a group of individuals involved in persistent social interaction, or a large social group sharing the same spatial or social territory, typically subject to the same political authority and dominant cultural expectations. Societies are characterized by patterns of relationships (social relations) between individuals who share a distinctive culture and institutions; a given society may be described as the sum total of such relationships among its constituent of members. Societies construct patterns of behavior by deeming certain actions or concepts as acceptable or unacceptable. These patterns of behavior within a given society are known as societal norms. Societies, and their norms, undergo gradual and perpetual changes. The rule of law is a principle directly related to the concepts of people's power and human rights. Because people's power means the right of citizens to directly or indirectly participate in the decision-making process. In this sense, the laws that are an expression of the people's will, adopted by the citizens through their elected representatives to the parliament or by themselves directly through a referendum, are the result, figuratively speaking, the fruit of the people's power. Human rights and freedoms are implemented through laws, in fact, the ultimate goal of laws is to protect people, their rights and freedoms. Law (in law) is a means of strengthening, developing and regulating social relations, which are considered the most important from the point of view of the interests of man, society and the state. The law is the highest authority document of state supreme representative bodies.

The law forms the basis of the state legal system and has the greatest legal force compared to the normative acts of all other bodies of the state. The rule of law means that the documents issued by state authorities and the actions of officials must be in accordance with the Constitution and laws.

In order to strengthen the principles of openness and transparency in the management of the state and society, in our daily activities, we need to fully ensure the implementation of the constitutional norm on citizens freedom of speech, receiving and distributing information. For this, first of all, it is necessary to improve the legislation on mass media, and we are actively working in this regard. In this regard, I would like all of us to understand that both public control and mass media are aimed at a single goal, that is, to please our people and improve their lives. Every state body must have its own page on social networks, provide detailed information about its activities, if necessary, every day. The rule of law allows a person to exercise his rights and freedoms without hindrance, his life, freedom, honor, dignity and other inviolable rights are guaranteed by the law to be peaceful, calm, free from any external influences, gives the opportunity to live without fear of violence and arbitrariness.

The rule of law also allows a person to participate in the process of accepting these documents that are binding on him or through his elected representatives, to influence the state administration, to exercise public control over the activities of state bodies, his protection of rights and freedoms through the court, provides the right to appeal to the court against the illegal actions of state bodies, officials, and public associations. If the rule of law is not ensured in society, people will lose confidence not only in today, but also in tomorrow, justice, equality and freedom will not be observed. In a society where the rule of law is not ensured, the economy will not develop, and economic reforms will not be effective. Because no one wants to bring their property and fortune to a place where the law does not work.

Freedom, justice, and equality are guaranteed in a state where the law prevails, the power's influence on the individual is limited, human rights are protected,

property rights are respected, and the judiciary is independent and effective. therefore, special attention is paid to the rule of law in the ratings compiled by various international organizations and research centers. Jumaladan The World Justice Project, an international non-governmental organization, annually conducts a special "Rule of Law Index" around the world. The "Transformation Index", "Bertelsman International Foundation", and the State Management Quality Index maintained by the World Bank list the rule of law as one of the indicators that ensure well-being. Administrative courts being established and laws on administrative procedures planned to be adopted are also important in ensuring the rule of law. In short, the rule of law is a guarantee of guaranteeing freedom, justice, equality, protection of human rights, and the formation of strong confidence in entrepreneurs for the stable growth of the country's economy.

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